

1 **Editorial: "Links between Cognition and Fitness: mechanisms and**
2 **constraints in the wild".**

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12 In the wild, animals frequently face environmental variations that can be predictable, for
13 example seasonal climate variation, or not, such as habitat destruction or climate change due to
14 the accelerating rate of anthropogenic activity. To cope with these variations, animals must
15 adjust their decisions to the changing conditions. Cognitive abilities, widely defined as all the
16 sensory, neurological, memory and decision processes used by individuals to interact with their
17 environment ([Shettleworth 2001](#)), can allow animals to gather and/or process information more
18 efficiently, better exploit their environment and flexibly adjust their behavior to facilitate
19 optimal responses to environmental changes ([Wyles et al. 1983](#); [Sol 2008](#)). Cognitive abilities
20 can thus be expected to be a key component of animal fitness in the wild, shaping the potential
21 for animal populations to rapidly adjust to a changing world.

22 A growing number of studies have recently explored whether cognitive performances
23 are positively linked with fitness components in the wild, but the results are not always in line
24 with such a prediction. Cognitive performances and fitness components can show positive links
25 (e.g. [Cauchard et al. 2013](#); [Ashton et al. 2018](#); [Sonnenberg et al. 2019](#)), negative links (e.g.
26 [Mery and Kawecki 2003](#)), no links (e.g. [Isden et al. 2013](#), [Huebner et al. 2018](#)), or even links
27 dependent on the context or on fitness components suggesting trade-offs between investment
28 in offspring and adult survival (e.g. [Cole et al. 2012](#)). Such varying results have frequently been
29 attributed to differences in the design of the cognitive tasks used (which have to be adapted to
30 the morphological and ecological constraints of the study model and site) and/or to other factors
31 that can affect behavioural performance in general (such as personality traits, motivation, age,
32 sex, etc.). However, once properly controlled for these potential biases ([Schubiger et al. 2020](#)),
33 these varying results must above all reflect the complex relationships between cognitive
34 abilities and selective pressures under various ecological and social contexts. Moreover,
35 whether the links, when detected, are causal remains unknown in most cases. Yet, identifying
36 the mechanisms underlying the links between cognitive performances and fitness components
37 and the constraints acting on these mechanisms is crucial to understand and predict how
38 selective pressures can shape the evolution of cognitive abilities in the wild. This is a major gap
39 in our understanding about how and when cognition can help animals to adapt to their changing
40 environments.

41 In this introduction to the themed issue "[Links between cognition and fitness:
42 mechanisms and constraints in the wild](#)", we present an overview of potential mechanisms that
43 could link inter-individual variation in cognitive ability and fitness components, and place the
44 15 contributions of this theme (5 reviews, 7 original research articles, 2 opinion pieces and 1
45 perspective) in context. Both direct and indirect mechanisms can link inter-individual variation
46 in cognitive ability to fitness components. Direct mechanisms involve a causal link between

47 cognition and fitness while indirect mechanisms involve cognition and fitness to be both
48 influenced simultaneously but independently by a third variable, creating a correlational link
49 between them.

50 Current literature on direct mechanisms suggests that individuals with better cognitive
51 abilities might make a better use of their environment for fitness-related decisions, but evidence
52 for such a causal mechanism is still very scarce, impeding our ability to draw general
53 conclusions. Szabo et al. ([2020](#)) highlighted in their review the cognitive abilities relevant for
54 species in conquering new habitats, targeting both invertebrate and vertebrate species, and
55 examined which cognitive traits could give species an advantage in a competitive, novel
56 environment. Going further, Cauchard et al. ([2017](#)) experimentally manipulated brood size in
57 wild breeding great tits to explore causal mechanisms between reproductive success and the
58 performance in solving a non-food motivated task presented at the nest. They showed that a
59 significant increase or decrease in brood size did not affect problem-solving performance, thus
60 excluding a direct causal relation through higher motivation to solve the task in more successful
61 pairs. Yet within treatments, task solver pairs still reached higher reproductive success
62 compared to non-solver pairs, which could at least partly be explained by a higher provisioning
63 rate. These results are in line with the hypothesis that problem-solvers may achieve higher
64 reproductive success through a better exploitation of the habitat. Such better habitat exploitation
65 may require individuals to process information about the habitat more efficiently. In order to
66 explore this question, White ([2020](#)) examined nest selection and its timing in nest-parasite
67 brown-headed cowbirds (*Molothrus ater*). By experimentally manipulating the number of eggs
68 present in mock nests and the timing of egg laying, White showed that female cowbirds relied
69 on social information, i.e. information obtained from the presence, behaviour or performance
70 of others ([Danchin et al. 2004](#)), to plan where, when and how many eggs to lay in a given host
71 nest. This ability to optimally use social information can be hypothesized to require different

72 cognitive abilities to process such information. In line with this prediction, the study by Morinay
73 Cauchard et al. ([2020](#)) experimentally showed that the use of social information for small-scale
74 nest site selection depended on learning performance in wild collared flycatchers (*Ficedula*
75 *albicollis*). Collared flycatchers are known to rely on heterospecific social information from
76 titmice for breeding decisions, which leads to fitness increase ([Forsman et al. 2002](#)). The study
77 by Morinay, Cauchard et al. ([2020](#)) revealed here a relation between learning performance and
78 the probability to copy nest preference by sympatric titmice. Overall, learning ability may be
79 particularly important to process information, driving the capacity to optimally deal with
80 environmental changes. To dig this idea deeper, a first comprehensive review by Barrett et al.
81 ([2019](#)) presented a compilation of theory and empirical evidence on how social learning can
82 help or hinder responses of organisms and thus species to human-induced rapid environmental
83 changes and how these changes can interfere with the transmission of social information. More
84 particularly, a second review by Greggor et al. ([2020](#)) focused on how learning in general may
85 allow individuals to avoid ecological traps driven by human-induced environmental changes,
86 depending on constraints, type of learning mechanism and individual factors such as
87 personality.

88 The ability to better use habitat may affect not only reproductive success but also
89 survival, especially in spatio-temporally varying environments. In their study, Meetke-
90 Hofmann et al ([2020](#)) explored the response to habitat novelty in the Gouldian finch (*Erythrura*
91 *gouldiae*), a polymorphic species showing a link between head color and behavioral
92 phenotypes. They showed that black-headed birds are more reluctant to enter a new dense
93 habitat than red-headed birds, which may negatively affect long-term population persistence to
94 habitat change since 70% of birds in the wild are black-headed. Yet, very little is currently
95 known regarding the links between cognitive abilities and survival. One reason for this may be
96 challenges when studying cognition in the wild ([Morand-Ferron et al. 2015](#)). In particular, most

97 studies in nature rely on limited sample size, preventing reliable survival analyses. To address
98 this issue in a laboratory setting, Matzel et al. ([2020](#)) took advantage of genetically
99 heterogeneous mice that express individual differences in general cognitive ability to explore
100 associated differences in behaviours known to be related to survival in this species. They found
101 that mice with a higher general cognitive ability score also showed a higher survival-readiness
102 score, and results suggested that heightened attention may drive this relationship. In their
103 review, Rochais et al. ([2022](#)) explored the existing literature linking cognition to survival in the
104 wild in order to highlight the cognitive traits that can be expected to be ecologically relevant
105 for survival, as well as the individual characteristics that might influence these relationships.
106 They discussed the challenges associated with investigating the links between cognition and
107 survival in natural populations, and proposed a methodological approach to ward off these
108 challenges.

109 Regarding indirect mechanisms, environmental variables such as habitat quality might
110 affect both cognitive abilities and fitness components simultaneously but separately, outside
111 any direct link between them. Using the extensive literature available on fish, Jacquin et al.
112 ([2020](#)) highlighted in their comprehensive perspective article how exposure to pollutants from
113 human-related activities can affect both cognition and fitness through various physiological and
114 behavioural (personality) mechanisms. This study thus emphasized the urgent need for future
115 studies to examine the links between ecotoxicology, cognitive ecology and evolutionary
116 ecology in a multi-stress framework to improve our ability to predict the effects of
117 anthropogenic stressors on wildlife. Parasitism is another environmental factor that can drive
118 an indirect link between cognition and fitness. In their review article, Ducatez et al. ([2020](#))
119 proposed three scenarios on how cognition could affect the reciprocal pressures that hosts and
120 parasites can exert on each other, shaping host-parasite eco-evolutionary dynamics. This review

121 revealed the need for experimental studies to distinguish between direct (causal) and indirect
122 (non-causal) effects of parasitism in the evolution of cognition.

123 Direct and indirect mechanisms may also operate simultaneously. For instance, in new
124 habitats, new constraints should favor individuals with cognitive abilities enhancing their
125 behavioral repertoire to cope with novel challenges and thereby achieve higher fitness. At the
126 same time, new habitats may also host new stressors such as pollutants and parasites, or affect
127 individual condition in general, impacting both cognition and fitness independently. In their
128 comparative study, Sayol et al. ([2020](#)) showed that brain size was positively associated with
129 urban tolerance, even if small-brained species can use alternative life history strategies, such as
130 a higher number of low value reproductive events, to succeed in urban environments.
131 Cognition-related differences in life-history strategies were also suggested in the study by
132 Johnson-Ulrich et al. ([2019](#)) in wild female spotted hyenas (*Crocuta crocuta*), where
133 innovativeness was linked to reproduction in multiple ways: innovative hyenas showed lower
134 cub survival but higher annual cub production compared to non-innovative hyenas, leading to
135 no overall difference between innovative and non-innovative hyenas in reproductive success.
136 Another example where both direct and indirect mechanisms may operate together is between-
137 species hybridization, whose effects on fitness have been frequently described, but potential
138 influence on cognition is yet largely ignored. Adding to a previous paper ([Rice and McQuillan](#)
139 [2018](#)) presenting how hybridization can negatively impact both hybrids' cognitive abilities and
140 fitness, thus creating an indirect link, Rice's perspective ([2020](#)) discussed further how
141 hybridization impact on cognition could lead to positive fitness consequences and indirectly
142 affect the expression of cognitive traits. By discussing how trade-offs between investment in
143 cognition and other important functions, coupled with individual variation, can complicate
144 patterns of selection on hybrid cognition, Rice ([2020](#)) questioned the role of cognitive

145 performance in the maintenance of species boundaries, and the links between hybridization and
146 the expression of, and selection on, cognitive traits in the wild.

147 Finally, when facing environmental variation, selection may favour flexible adjustment
148 ability, and this may also apply to cognitive performance. In a mini-review, Cauchoix et al.
149 (2020) compiled current evidence for such plasticity in cognitive performance, called ‘cognitive
150 performance plasticity’, in response to environmental conditions and proposed methodological
151 approaches to measure it, highlighting its role when exploring the repeatability of cognitive
152 performance.

153 Overall, this body of research provides the first comprehensive overview of constraints
154 influencing the evolution of cognition in the wild, highlights the multiple ways by which
155 cognition can be linked to fitness and the needs for further research on this question. In addition
156 to presenting novel results and methods, several authors presented a number of compelling ideas
157 and perspectives that will help us to improve our understanding of this field.

158

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165 **Conflict of Interest**

166 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or
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